

[Insert Site Logo]

Participant Information Sheet

Interventional Study - Adult providing own consent

[Insert site name]

Proteotyping microorganisms in human distal oesophagus under normal and disease conditions

Proteotyping microorganisms in oesophagus

[Coordinating Principal Investigator/ Principal Investigator/ Associate Investigator]

[Location]

You are invited to take part in a research study investigating on the change in bacterial communities in healthy and diseased oesophagus

1. The purpose of the study:

To obtain a clearer understanding of the bacteria in the human food pipe (oesophagus) and how oesophageal diseases can affect the bacterial population. The study is being conducted by Dr Jerry Zhou, Dr Vincent Ho (Gastroenterologist) and Ms Prapti Shrestha at the School of Medicine, Western Sydney University, in collaboration with 3 gastroenterologists, [collaborators name, site location]

2. How can you be involved?

During gastroscopy examination, an oesophageal biopsy (removal of small piece of tissue, 1-2mm diameter from lower oesophagus) is safely taken out using biopsy forceps. It is one of the most frequently performed endoscopic procedures by an experienced Gastroenterologist.

Diagram of biopsy forceps collecting a tissue sample

For this study, an oesophageal brush and a biopsy sample is required. If the oesophagus appears irregular another biopsy will be collected for routine histopathology analysis. If the oesophagus appears normal, only one brush and a biopsy will be taken to be used for this research.

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Most patients do not feel the biopsy taken due to the sedative medication. However, in some cases there can be little or no discomfort after the gastroscopy. The procedure would usually take 15 – 20 mins. The Participant Consent form needs to be signed before the procedure.

The biopsy samples will be transported to Translational Gastroenterology laboratory at Western Sydney University (Campbelltown campus) where the proteins would be extracted from the sample for further molecular analysis while the tissue gets destroyed

3. Are there any risks?

Often there can be minimal bleeding at the biopsy site which does not leave a scar. Serious complications are rare during gastroscopy, less than 1 in 1000 chance of occurring.

Rare complications may include:

Bleeding—Bleeding can be present following removal of a piece of tissue. In rare cases, such bleeding may require a blood transfusion

Infection—Routine gastroscopies consist of an examination and biopsy, and risk of infection is low. Most infections are minor and can be treated with antibiotics.

Tearing of the oesophagus — A tear in the oesophagus may require hospitalisation and sometimes surgery to repair it. The risk of this complication is very low (1 of every 11,000 diagnostic gastroscopies)

You can reduce your risk of complications by carefully following your doctor's instructions for preparing for an endoscopy, such as fasting and stopping certain medications.

The gastroscopy will always be performed by a trained medical professional. Our gastroenterology specialists) will be present during the procedure to handle complications or provide additional information.

4. What will happen to information about me?

By signing the consent form you consent to the research team collecting and using personal information about you for the research project. In addition, the researchers would like to access your medical records to obtain general information relevant to this study (age, gender, BMI, upper GI history, medication history: antibiotics and protein pump inhibitors, gastroscopy histopathology).

All aspects of the study, including results, will be strictly confidential and only the investigators named above will have access to information on participants. A report of the study may be submitted for publication, but individual participants will not be identifiable in the report.

5. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

While we intend that this research furthers medical knowledge and may improve interpretation and assessment of upper GI disorders test results, it would not be of direct benefit to you. No incentive/payment or reimbursement is provided to participants.

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Participation is entirely voluntary, if you do sign the form and wish to withdraw any time later, your samples would be excluded from the study. Whatever your decision, please be assured that it will not affect your medical treatment or your relationship with medical staff.

6. Who has reviewed the research project?

All human research in Australia is reviewed by the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC). The ethical aspects of this research have been approved by the HREC of the [institution]. This project is carried out according to the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007). This statement has been developed to protect the interests of people who agree to participate in human research studies.

When you have read this information, a member of the research team will discuss it with you further and answer any questions you may have. If you would like to know more at any stage, please feel free to contact:

Dr Jerry Zhou on 02 4620 3865

Dr Vincent Ho on 02 4634 4001

Ms Prapti Shrestha on 04 1654 8578

If you have any complaints about any aspect of the project, the way it is being conducted or any questions about being a research participant in general, then you may contact: Ms Felicity Lindfield, Nepean Hospital Patient Representative

Ph. (02) 4734 3228,

E: Felicity.Lindfield@health.nsw.gov.au

Reviewing HREC Details: NBMLHD HREC, HREC Executive Officer

Ph. (02) 4734 1998

E: NBMLHD-ResearchOffice@health.nsw.gov.au

Local RGO Office Contact: NBMLHD RGO, Research Governance Officer,

Ph. (02) 4734 1998

E: NBMLHD-RGO@health.nsw.gov.au

This study has been approved by the Ethics Review Committee of the South Western Sydney Local Health District. Any person with concerns or complaints about the conduct of a research study should contact the Ethics and Research Governance Office,

Mail: Locked Bag 7103,

LIVERPOOL BC, NSW, 1871

Phone: 02 8738 8304, Fax: 02 8738 8310

Email: SWSLHD-Ethics@health.nsw.gov.au

Project no. :HE16/075

Sincerely,

Dr Jerry Zhou

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